

Fluorine containing Biologically Active Agents : Synthesis of some New Pyrimidine Derivatives

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Various biological activities have been attributed to pyrimidine derivatives¹. Recent investigations have shown that the introduction of fluorine into pyrimidines produces compounds showing diverse biological activities. Encouraged by these observations, we have undertaken a comprehensive programme for developing new fluorine containing condensed pyrimidines as possible antimicrobial agents.

2-Amino-3-cyano-4,6-disubstituted pyridine (**1**) has been prepared by Michael reaction² by the cyclisation of chalcone with dicyanomethane in 1:1 molar ratio in the presence of ammonium acetate. The condensation of **1** with urea, thiourea, formamide and carbon disulphide afforded 4-amino-5,7-disubstituted-pyrido[2,3-d]pyrimidin-2(1H)-ones (**2**), 4-amino-5,7-disubstituted-pyrido[2,3-d]pyrimidin-2(1H)-thiones (**3**), 4-amino-5,7-disubstituted-pyrido[2,3-d]pyrimidines (**4**) and 5,7-disubstituted-pyrido[2,3-d]pyrimidin-2,4(1H,3H)-dithiones (**5**) respectively (Scheme 1).

(72%), m.p. > 360°, v_{\max} 3 095 (NH), 3 435–3 330 (NH₂), 1700 cm⁻¹ (C=O), ¹H nmr δ 8.21 (NH), 6.70–7.70 (m, ArH, NH₂), ¹⁹F nmr δ –108.887, –111.69 (Ar-F); **2b** (62%), 325–27°, v_{\max} 3 080 (NH), 3 450–3 320 (NH₂), 1 680 (C=O), ¹H nmr δ 8.20 (NH), 6.85–8.80 (m, ArH, NH₂), ¹⁹F nmr δ –108.13

Scheme 1

Experimental

4-Amino-5,7-disubstituted-pyrido[2,3-d]pyrimidin-2(1H)-ones (2a, b) : A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) and urea (0.02 mol) was heated on an oil-bath at 120–30° for 2 h with constant stirring. The temperature was raised to 180° and finally the mixture was heated at 230° for 2 h.

The residue thus obtained was washed with water, saturated NaHCO₃ solution and cold ethanol and crystallised from DMF-ethanol (1 : 2) : **2a**

4-Amino-5,7-disubstituted-pyrido[2,3-d]pyrimidin-2(1H)-thiones (3a, b) : A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) and thiourea (0.02 mol) was heated on an oil-bath at 120–30° for 2 h with constant stirring. The temperature was then raised to 180° and finally the mixture was heated at 230° for 2 h. The residue thus obtained was washed with water, saturated NaHCO₃ solution and cold ethanol and crystallised from DMF-ethanol (1 : 2) : **3a**

(55%), m.p. > 360°, ν_{\max} 3 150 (NH), 3 450–3 325 (NH₂), 1 160 (C=S), 1 430, 1 470, 1 555 cm⁻¹ (NHC=S), ¹H nmr δ 8.25 (NH) 6.90–8.50 (m, ArH, NH₂), ¹⁹F nmr δ -106.628, -108.713 (Ar-F); **3b** (61%), 268–70°, ν_{\max} 3 140 (NH), 3 440–3 330 (NH₂), 1 200 (C=S), 1 450, 1 470, 1 550 cm⁻¹ (NH-C=S), ¹H nmr δ 8.32 (NH), 6.72–7.95 (m, ArH, NH₂), ¹⁹F nmr δ -104.749 (Ar-F).

4-Amino-5,7-disubstituted-pyrido[2,3-d]pyrimidine (4b, b): A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) and formamide (0.04 mol) was refluxed on an oil-bath for 15 h. After cooling, the reaction mixture was poured into ice and the resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from DMF-ethanol (1:2): **4a** (62%), m.p. 260°, ν_{\max} 3 410–3 335 cm⁻¹ (NH₂), ¹H nmr δ 6.69–8.20 (m, ArH, NH₂), ¹⁹F nmr δ -106.397, -108.887 (Ar-F); **4b** (57%), 250–53°, ν_{\max} 3 435–3 300 cm⁻¹ (NH₂), ¹H nmr δ 6.95–8.82 (m, ArH, NH₂), ¹⁹F nmr δ -104.11 (Ar-F).

5,7-Disubstituted-pyrido[2,3-d]pyrimidin-2,4(1H,3H)-dithiones (5a, b): A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) and carbon disulphide (0.04 mol) in pyridine (15 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 10–15 h. After cooling, excess pyridine was removed by distillation and the resulting solid was washed with water, saturated NaHCO₃ solution and cold ethanol and crystallised from DMF-ethanol (1 : 2): **5a** (58%), m.p. 257°, ν_{\max} 3 095 (NH), 1 200 (C=S), 1 455, 1 490, 1 575 cm⁻¹ (-NH-C=S), ¹H nmr δ 8.45 (NH), 6.73–8.30 (m, ArH, NH₂), ¹⁹F nmr δ -112.015, -115.200 (Ar-F); **5b** (57%), 290–92°, ν_{\max} 1 180 (C=S), 1 430, 1 480, 1 585 cm⁻¹ (NH-C=S), ¹H nmr δ 8.35 (NH), 6.75–7.75 (m, ArH, NH₂), ¹⁹F nmr δ -106.22 (Ar-F).

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, ¹H and ¹⁹F nmr spectra on a FX 90Q JEOL spectrometer (90 MHz). ¹H nmr spectra were taken in DMSO-d₆ using

TMS as an internal standard. The chemical shifts are given in ppm downfield from tetramethylsilane.

Antimicrobial activity: All the compounds were screened for their antimicrobial activity at concentration 100 µg/disc in agar media³, using streptomycin in antibacterial and mycostatin in anti-fungal activity as reference compounds. All the compounds showed activity against gram-positive bacterium *Staphylococcus aureus* and gram-negative bacterium *Escherichia coli*. Compound **5a** showed maximum zone of inhibition (13.4 mm) against *E. coli*, while **3a** showed maximum zone of inhibition (13.5 mm) against *S. aureus*. The other compounds showed moderate zone of inhibition (8.6–12.0 mm).

The compound **5b** showed maximum antifungal activity with inhibition area (12.6 mm) against fungus *Curvularia lunata*. The rest of the compounds were moderately active against *Aspergillus flavus*, *Curvularia lunata*, *Fusarium moniliformae* and *Aspergillus niger* (6.3–10.2 mm).

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